

Kinetic spectrophotometric determination of titanium(IV) at trace level with bromopyrogallol red in ionic/non-ionic surfactant mixed micellar media

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Ti^{IV} inhibited the decolourization reaction of bromopyrogallol red (BPR) in a mixed micellar medium composed of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) and nonylphenoxypolyethoxyethanol (OP). Based on the effect, a kinetic spectrophotometric method has been developed for the determination of trace Ti^{IV}. The method is very sensitive. Under the recommended conditions, the molar absorptivity is as high as $4.0 \times 10^6 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, the highest value ever reported. The limit of detection is as low as 0.2 ng cm^{-3} .

Micelles, microemulsions, etc., are organic microheterogeneous media. The use of these media in analytical reactions for developing new kinetic-based determinations or improving previously established kinetic methods has received considerable attention in recent years¹. We have studied several analytical reactions in these media, especially in ionic/non-ionic surfactant mixed micellar media². Results obtained seem most promising for further increase in absorptiometric sensitivity for determining metal ions with dyes. Our preliminary studies show that Ti^{IV} is a highly sensitive inhibitor for the decolourization reaction of bromopyrogallol red (BPR) in a mixed micellar medium composed of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) and nonylphenoxypolyethoxyethanol (OP). Based on the inhibitory effect of Ti^{IV}, a kinetic spectrophotometric method for the determination of Ti^{IV} at trace level has been developed and reported in this paper. Results show that the present method is very sensitive. Its high sensitivity and low limit of detection resulted from the large difference in the reaction rate between systems with and without Ti^{IV} and the high molar ratio of BPR to Ti^{IV}, which should be attributed to the mixed micelles.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra : Fig. 1 gives absorption spectra of the sample (systems with and without Ti^{IV}, hereafter referred to as samples and blanks, respectively) and the blank. The result reveals that Ti^{IV} has an obvious inhibitory effect on the decolourization reaction of BPR. Proper choice of the reaction condition can make the system without Ti^{IV} decolourize completely at 542 nm (the absorp-

Fig. 1. Absorption spectra : (---) sample against water, (—) blank against water, (-·-) sample against blank; temp. = 90°, pH = 2.0, [BPR] = $6 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, [CTAB] = 0.1%, [OP] = 0.8%, [H₂O₂] = $1 \times 10^{-3}\%$, Ti = 10 ng cm^{-3} .

tion maximum of the sample against the blank), and make the system with Ti^{IV} remain almost unchanged.

Effect of temperature : At room temperature, the reaction rate was very slow for both the sample and the blank. No obvious changes in their absorption spectra were observed even if they were kept for 30 min at 30°. At higher temperature (>60°), the reaction rate was accelerated for both the blank and the sample and, moreover, their dif-

ference in reaction rate was enlarged. At 90°, only 7 min were needed for complete decolourization of the blank (Fig. 2). By this time, however, the absorbance of the sample decreased by less than 5%. When the temperature exceeded 95°, the sample had begun to decolourize prior to complete decolourization of the blank. For comparison, the *A-t* curves at 100° for the sample and the blank are included in Fig. 2. It can be seen that the net absorbance of the sample at 100° is less than that at 90°.

Effect of surfactants : At a given concentration of CTAB, the reaction rates of both the blank and the sample increased with the increase of the concentration of OP, but they showed different dependence on the concentration of OP. The rate of the sample was much slower than that of the corresponding blank. Further increase of the concentration of OP, however, caused the solutions of both the sample and the blank to be turbid if the concentration of CTAB was not high, thereby resulting in incomplete

Fig. 2. Plots of absorbance (against water) of (●) sample and (x) blank versus reaction time at (—) 90° and (---) 100°; conditions same as in Fig. 1 except pH = 2.32.

decolourization of the blank at 542 nm. To avoid phase separation, it was necessary to keep the concentration of CTAB high. If [OP] was fixed at 0.8% (w/v), then [CTAB] should be no less than 0.05% (w/v). When [CTAB] exceeded 0.15% (w/v), however, appreciable decrease in the reaction rate for both the sample and the blank was observed. Moreover, the sample had begun to decolourize at a perceivable rate prior to complete decolourization of the blank. Results showed that the optimum concentration of CTAB was $0.10 \pm 0.02\%$ for 0.8% OP. If [CTAB] was fixed at 0.1% and an error of $\pm 5\%$ in absorbance was tolerated for $10 \text{ ng cm}^{-3} \text{ Ti}^{\text{IV}}$, then the permissible concentration range of OP was $0.8 \pm 0.1\%$.

Effect of pH : The effect of pH on the net absorbance (ΔA) of the sample (against the blank) is given in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Effects of pH on the net absorbance (ΔA): (●) of sample (against blank) and (x) on optimum reaction time (*t*); conditions same as in Fig. 1 except pH.

The net absorbance value at a given pH was the highest one, which was obtained by proper choice of the reaction time. The optimum reaction time values at different pHs are also included in Fig. 3.

The optimum reaction time means the time by which the blank is decolourized completely (from purple red to golden yellow) at 542 nm while absorbance of the sample remains almost unchanged. This value was obtained by plotting absorbance (against water) vs time for the sample and its corresponding blank. The results showed that over the pH range of 2.0–2.7, ΔA was not only maximum but also stable. In subsequent experiments, a buffer solution with a pH value of 2.32 was used; its optimum volume was $2.0 \pm 0.5 \text{ ml}$.

Effect of BPR : The net absorbance (ΔA) increased first rapidly and then slowly with the increase of the concentration of BPR, which was accompanied by a gradual hypsochromic shift of the peak of the sample (against the blank) (from 542 to 532 nm). Over the concentration range of $(2.5\text{--}4.0) \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the increment in ΔA was very small. Considering that the increase of the concentration of BPR gave rise to long reaction time and poor reproducibility, the final concentration of BPR was fixed at $2.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. By the way, it is the mixed micelles that make high concentration of BPR in water possible.

Effect of H_2O_2 : The mixed micelles at 90° stimulated the decolourization reaction of BPR (micellar catalysis) but more time (>20 min) was needed for complete decolourization of the blank containing high concentration of BPR in the absence of H_2O_2 . Although H_2O_2 considerably shortened the time needed for complete decolourization of BPR at 532 nm, yet large amounts of H_2O_2 reduced the difference in reaction rate between the sample and the blank. Experiment showed that the optimum volume for 0.01%

H₂O₂ ranged from 0.4 to 1.2 ml. Under the recommended conditions, 9.5 min were needed for complete decolourization of the blank.

Analytical characteristic : Over the range 2–10 ng cm⁻³ Ti^{IV}, ΔA increased linearly with the content of Ti^{IV}. The linear regression equation was : ΔA = 0.0893 C_{Ti} (ng cm⁻³) + 0.132 (r = 0.996). The limit of detection (based on three times the standard deviation of the blank) was 0.2 ng cm⁻³. For 5.0 ng cm⁻³ Ti^{IV}, the relative standard deviation (RSD) of nine replicate determinations was 3.8%. To our knowledge, the present method seems to be the most sensitive method ever reported for the determination of titanium(IV)³. Its molar absorptivity was as high as 4.0 × 10⁶ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹. The high sensitivity and low limit of detection resulted from the large difference in the reaction rate between the sample and the blank and the high molar ratio of BPR to Ti^{IV}, which should be attributed to the mixed micelles.

Effect of other metal ions : To explore the possibility of application of the inhibitory effect of Ti^{IV}, effects of other metal ions (5 ng cm⁻³) on the determination of 5 ng cm⁻³ Ti^{IV} were examined separately. Results showed that Mo^{VI}, W^{VI}, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Ga^{III}, Ge^{IV} and Zr^{IV} at 5 ng cm⁻³ level interfered with the determination of Ti^{IV}, but Cd^{II}, Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Al^{III}, Sb^{III}, Hg^{II}, Ag^I, Pt^{II}, Mn^{II}, Ce^{IV}, Bi^{III}, Co^{II}, Ca^{II}, As^{III}, As^V and Pb^{II} at the same level did not if a relative error of ± 5% was tolerated. The tolerance limits (ng) of these foreign metal ions were as follows : As^{III}, As^V, Pb^{II} (≥ 2000); Bi^{III}, Co^{II}, Ca^{II} (1000); Hg^{II}, Ag^I, Pt^{II}, Mn^{II} (200); Al^{III}, Sb^{III} (100); Cd^{II}, Cr^{III}, Ce^{IV}, Fe^{III} (50).

Application to a synthetic sample : Based on the effects of foreign metal ions, a mixture of Pb^{II}, Fe^{III} and Ti^{IV} with a weight ratio of 4 : 2 : 1 was prepared to validate the present method. Under the optimum conditions, the standard addition method was applied for the determination of Ti^{IV} in the synthetic sample which contained 5.0 ng Ti^{IV} per milliliter. After seven replicate determinations, the average Ti^{IV} content in the sample was found to be 5.06 ± 0.23 ng per milliliter with recovery ranging from 96.6% to 105.8%. This result indicates that the proposed method is suitable for the determination of trace amounts of titanium. If an appropriate separation technique is incorporated, the present method could be applied to analyze Ti^{IV} in real samples.

Experimental

Reaction systems were thermostated by water from a model 501 thermostatic bath (Shanghai Experimental Equipment Factory). The UV-vis absorption spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-240 spectrophotometer fitted with a matched pair of 1 cm long quartz cell. The pH was measured using a PHS-2 pH meter (Shanghai Experimental Equipment Factory).

Unless otherwise stated, all reagents used were of

analytical grade and their solutions were prepared by weighing with triple-distilled water as solvent.

Ti^{IV} stock solution, 1 μg cm⁻³ (containing 0.5 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄) was prepared by dissolving a known amount of spectrally pure TiO₂ powder in concentrated H₂SO₄ in the presence of (NH₄)₂SO₄ (the detailed procedure was reported elsewhere⁴). Ti^{IV} working solution (10.0 ng cm⁻³) was prepared freshly each day by diluting 1.0 ml of the stock solution to 100 ml with water (the final concentration of H₂SO₄ was 0.05 mol dm⁻³). Bromopyrogallol red (BPR) (Merck) solution (1 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³) was prepared using 1 : 1 (v/v) ethanol-water as solvent. A 1.0% (w/v) solution of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide and a 8.0% (w/v) solution of nonylphenoxypolyethoxyethanol (OP) (Wuhan Tongxing Chemical Reagent Plant, China) were prepared. H₂O₂ solution, (0.01%, w/v) was prepared by appropriate dilution of the concentrated solution (the content was checked by redox titration with KMnO₄). A buffer solution of pH 2.32 was prepared by mixing 1 mol dm⁻³ NaAc (50 ml) with 1 mol dm⁻³ HCl (51 ml) and finally diluting to 250 ml (checked with pH meter).

Procedure : To a mixture of 1 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ BPR (2.5 ml), 1.0% CTAB (1.0 ml), 8.0% OP (1.0 ml) and the buffer solution (2.0 ml), was added an aliquot of 10.0 ng cm⁻³ Ti^{IV} working solution (as sample) or an aliquot of 0.05 mol dm⁻³ H₂SO₄ (as blank), then diluted to 9 ml. A 0.01% (1.0 ml) was added, mixed well, put into a thermostatic water-bath quickly and kept it for 9.5 min at 90°, then cooled. Its absorption spectrum was recorded over the range 360–600 nm (against water) or of the sample (against the blank) at 532 nm.

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